

Economic analysis of Czech Walpurgis “Witches’ Night”: local sales and revenues

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Abstract

The paper provides an economic analysis of Czech Walpurgis “Witches’ Night” (called “Pálení čarodějnic” and held annually on the 30th of April as a very popular but unofficial holiday). The research employs the open-source intelligence (OSINT) of satellite images with the patterns of bonfires used as a proxy for celebration density over Czechia and translates them into estimated local sales and revenues.

Our results reveal that Czech Walpurgis “Witches’ Night” may generate around CZK 107 million (\$5 million) in turnover nationwide. Estimated gross operating profit reaches around CZK 44 million (\$2 million). From the spatial point of view, the strongest commercial hotspot is not just Prague, the capital of Czechia, but especially Central Bohemia District which accounts for about \$1.39 million in revenues. It is followed by South Moravia District with about \$0.99 million in revenues, Moravian-Silesia with \$0.42 million and South Bohemia with about \$0.38 million.

Nowadays, Czech Walpurgis “Witches’ Night” represents a good example how ancient rituals can be transformed into an efficient and profitable operational framework for local economies. However, even though the holiday remains highly popular in Czechia, it is likely to face profound transformation due to the sustainable economy concerns and climate change issues.

Keywords: economic assessment, Walpurgis Night, “Witches’ Night”, open-source intelligence, local economy, Czechia

1. Introduction

Czech Walpurgis “Witches’ Night” (also called “Saint Philip’s and Saint Jakob’s Night”) is one of the most visually striking annual customs observed in modern Czechia. Not an official Czech holiday, it is vigorously celebrated on the 30th of April with stacked pyres and straw witches awaiting incineration, parents carrying bundles of sticks, beer taps assembled outdoors, loudspeakers, children in Halloween-like costumes, and volunteer firefighter brigade watching over all of this. Interpretation ties the date to Beltane - a spring fire festival associated with the Celtic ritual calendar (Fig. 1).

Beltane Walpurgis Night

Fig. 1. Transformation from Beltane to Walpurgis “Witches Night”

Source: Own results

In some places the event is celebrated on public sports grounds, municipal parks, lakesides, castle courtyards, open meadows, and village commons where the celebration becomes a managed civic festival. The event might be viewed as a hybrid of Guy Fawkes Bonfire Night, 4th of July fireworks, and Halloween (which also has roots in the Celtic calendar as another important mystical holiday Samhain) [1,2]. Figure 2 depicts the most notorious attributes of Czech Walpurgis “Witches’ Night”.

Fig. 2. Main attributes of Czech Walpurgis “Witches’ Night” (“Pálení čarodějnic”)

Source: Own results

This paper studies the phenomenon of Czech Walpurgis “Witches’ Night” as an economic institution that generates considerable revenues and profits. Our methodology employs open-source intelligence (OSINT) that involves the analysis of satellite images over Czechia on April 30th with the patterns of bonfires as a proxy for celebration density and translating those clusters into estimated local sales of drinks and refreshments and the revenues they might potentially generate.

2. Historic overview

The historical background of Czech Walpurgis “Witches’ Night” can probably be linked to Beltane - a spring fire festival associated with the Celtic ritual calendar and marking midway between the spring equinox and summer solstice. Nevertheless, over 2,000 years the ritual has undergone many alterations and modifications. In 1910, Czech ethnographer Čeněk Zibrt wrote that the custom of burning the witch effigy during the Czech Walpurgis “Witches’ Night” on the 30th of April was not as indigenous in Czech lands but was probably borrowed from western or German lands [3].

Czech “Witches’ Night” celebration can be put within a broader European context of spring fires and Walpurgis Night as modern participants often invoke a vaguely ancient or pagan past because it makes the event more attractive and more legitimate in the present [4]. Table 1 that follows provides an overview of the historical roots versus modern customs for the Czech Walpurgis “Witches’ Night”.

Table 1. Czech Walpurgis “Witches’ Night”: historical ritual and modern event

Aspect	Historical focus	Modern focus
Primary goal	Protection of livestock and crops	Socializing and entertainment
Location	High hills and crossroads	Sports fields and backyard gardens
Key activity	Throwing flaming brooms	Roasting sausages and drinking beer

Source: Own results

The late 19th and early 20th centuries brought stronger attempts at control as bans by church and civic authorities were imposed to suppress the custom as dangerous superstition. Under Nazi occupation during WWII, blackout conditions made open fires problematic and further constrained the old pattern of hilltop burning. Under Communist rule (1948-1989), the tradition was not eliminated but rather repurposed. The holiday was renamed “Fires of Peace” (“Mírové ohně”), controlled by the authorities, and required to end early to get the workers rested for the following May Labor Day mandatory parade [5].

The fall of the Communist regime and the post-1989 transformation offered favorable climate for seeking “roots” and forms of spirituality outside official church institutions fostering event organization and publicity. Today, the celebration of Czech Walpurgis Witches’ Night is mostly organized on thousands of sites throughout the country and in its dominant format has become a public social event rather than a dense ritual system and use the element of fire like, for example, Burning Man festival in Nevada desert [6-8]. Some individuals use the night of April the 30th to engage in Pagan rituals, host underground techno parties in forests, or gather at mystical Celtic sites. One of the popular places for celebrating Czech Walpurgis “Witches’ Night” (or Beltane) in Prague is on the hilltop over Vltava River at the site of the ruins of former Závist Celtic Oppidum (located 1.5 km from Dolní Břežany), once the largest of its kind.

3. Materials and methods

According to the satellite data, the Czech Walpurgis Night celebrations can be seen from space in good weather [9]. National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) satellites that photograph the territory of Czechia regularly capture massive fires over the country on April 30th [10]. This research uses open-source satellite images taken on April 30th in 2018, 2019, and 2023 (see Figures 3-5). The fires are visible as purple dots, and their distribution suggests the locations of pyres and witches’ effigies.

Fig. 3. NOAA satellite image of Czechia, April 30th, 2018
Source: [11]

Fig. 4. Satellite image of Czechia, April 30th, 2019
Source: [12]

Fig. 5. Satellite image of Czechia, April 30th, 2023
Source: [13]

The revenue modeling scenario used in this study estimates direct event turnover under different attendance assumptions of Czech Walpurgis “Witches’ Night”. It does not attempt to measure wider spillovers, such as sales at nearby pubs after the official event ends, transport expenditures, or opportunity costs of volunteer labor. Those effects are real but exceed the available evidence. The core revenue identity for a local event j can be represented as:

$$R_j = \Sigma (q_{ij} * p_{ij}) + T_j + S_j \quad (1)$$

where q_{ij} is the quantity sold of items i , p_{ij} is the price of item i , T_j is ticket revenue, and S_j is sponsorship or subsidy revenue. For most free-entry village events, the dominant directly observable components are food and beverage sales, so the most important products are beer and roasted sausages or comparable grilled items. Beer sales are modeled as:

$$B_j = A_j * \alpha * \beta * \gamma \quad (2)$$

where A_j is attendance, α is the adult share of attendees, β is the share of adults purchasing draught beer, and γ is the average number of half liters purchased by each beer buyer. Beer revenue can be expressed as

$$RB_j = B_j * p_{beer} \quad (3)$$

In the same fashion, sausage sales are modeled as:

$$U_j = A_j * \delta * \eta \quad (4)$$

where δ is the share of all attendees purchasing a sausage and η is the mean number of sausages per buyer. Sausage revenue can be expressed as:

$$RU_j = U_j * p_{sausage} \quad (5)$$

4. Main results

Our model uses the spatial distribution of fires visible on open-source satellite imagery from the average night of the 30th of April as a proxy for Czech Walpurgis “Witches’ Night” celebration intensity. Each visible fire or fire cluster is interpreted as a potential event node. Denser clusters are treated as indicating either a larger number of events, larger average attendance, or both. The model parameters are presented in Table 3 below.

Table 3. Parameters of Czech Walpurgis “Witches’ Night” national economic model

Variable	Symbol	Assumption	Interpretation
Beer consumption per attendee	q_b	1.8 beers	Moderate event consumption
Sausage consumption per attendee	q_s	0.7 sausages	Not every attendee purchases one full unit
Average beer price	p_b	CZK 55	Typical kiosk or local event price
Average sausage price	p_s	CZK 70	Typical sausage (špekáček) or equivalent grilled sausage
Beer gross margin	m_b	0.45	Gross contribution after direct product cost
Sausage gross margin	m_s	0.35	Gross contribution after direct product cost
High-profit attendance	A_H	90 people	Large metropolitan or suburban events
Medium-profit attendance	A_M	60 people	Standard town-level events
Low-profit attendance	A_L	35 people	Small dispersed rural events
High-profit demand multiplier	u_H	1.4	Strong demand in metro and suburban areas
Medium-profit demand multiplier	u_M	1.1	Typical regional demand
Low-profit demand multiplier	u_L	0.8	Weaker commercial intensity in rural areas

Source: Own results

Figure 6 below shows the estimated commercial profit zones of Czech Walpurgis Night based on the satellite images of bonfires all over Czechia (darker areas signify higher profit zones).

Fig. 6. Distribution of profit zones during Czech Walpurgis “Witches’ Night” (April 30th)
Source: Own results

From Figure 6, one can see that the satellite images indicate the strongest concentration of fires during Czech Walpurgis “Witches’ Night” in Prague and especially in Central Bohemia District, followed by South Moravia and several regional clusters. Tables 4 and 5 report the regional turnover and gross profits by regions and nationally (whole Czechia).

Table 4. Regional turnover and gross profit of Czech Walpurgis “Witches’ Night” by regions

Region	Profit class	Events	Turnover per event (CZK)	Gross profit per event (CZK)	Total turnover (CZK)	Total gross profit (CZK)
Praha	High	250	18,648.0	7,774.2	4,662,000	1,943,550
Středočeský	High	1,550	18,648.0	7,774.2	28,904,400	12,050,010
Jihomoravský	High	1,100	18,648.0	7,774.2	20,512,800	8,551,620
Moravskoslezský	Medium	900	9,768.0	4,072.2	8,791,200	3,664,980
Plzeňský	Medium	650	9,768.0	4,072.2	6,349,200	2,646,930
Jihočeský	Medium	800	9,768.0	4,072.2	7,814,400	3,257,760
Ústecký	Medium	650	9,768.0	4,072.2	6,349,200	2,646,930
Liberecký	Medium	350	9,768.0	4,072.2	3,418,800	1,425,270
Královéhradecký	Medium	450	9,768.0	4,072.2	4,395,600	1,832,490
Pardubický	Medium	380	9,768.0	4,072.2	3,711,840	1,547,436
Olomoucký	Medium	550	9,768.0	4,072.2	5,372,400	2,239,710
Zlínský	Medium	450	9,768.0	4,072.2	4,395,600	1,832,490
Vysočina	Low	400	4,144.0	1,727.6	1,657,600	691,040
Karlovarský	Low	250	4,144.0	1,727.6	1,036,000	431,900
Total		8,730			107,371,040	44,762,116

Source: Own results

Table 5: National summary by profit zone

Profit zone	Regions mainly represented	Events	Share of all events	Total turnover (CZK)	Total gross profit (CZK)
High	Praha, Středočeský, Jihomoravský	2,900	33.2%	54,079,200	22,545,180
Medium	Major regional urban belts	5,180	59.3%	50,598,240	21,093,996
Low	Sparse rural interior and periphery	650	7.4%	2,693,600	1,122,940
Total	Czechia	8,730	100.0%	107,371,040	44,762,116

Source: Own results

The national totals for the Czech Walpurgis “Witches’ Night” can be calculated as follows: $TR_{CZ} = 107,371,040$ CZK and $GP_{CZ} = 44,762,116$ CZK. Overall, the model yields approximately CZK 107.4 million (€4.41 million or \$5.18 million) in beer-and-sausage turnover and CZK 44.8 million (€1.84 million or \$2.16 million) in gross operating profit.

Our results suggest that Prague and Central Bohemia Region zones form the single most commercially important Czech Walpurgis “Witches’ Night” market in Czechia. South Moravia District constitutes the second strongest high-profit zone, while a broad set of medium-profit regions jointly contributes almost as much to national gross profit as the top three high-profit regions. This means that the ritual's economic significance is not exclusively metropolitan but depends on the coexistence of one dominant metropolitan cluster and numerous medium-sized regional markets.

5. Conclusions

Overall, our results demonstrate that Czech Walpurgis “Witches’ Night” is a historically layered and institutionally adaptive tradition whose persistence depends on its capacity to absorb new meanings without losing its calendrical and visual core. The celebrations on the night of the 30th of April have become an important urban cultural and economic event. Our estimated nationwide turnover of Czech Walpurgis “Witches’ Night” from beer and sausage sales reaches approximately CZK 107.4 million, with gross operating profit of about CZK 44.8 million. The largest commercial zone is Prague together with Central Bohemia District, followed by South Moravia District and a broad belt of medium-profit regional markets. It is likely that in the future Czech Walpurgis “Witches’ Night” is going to continue to transform in the face of economic, social, and environmental challenges. Bonfires may become smaller, more spatially controlled, and more closely tied to registered organizers. Reusable cups, cleaner fuel, stricter sitting, and more explicit fire-watch arrangements may become standard. In extreme years, symbolic substitutes-light installations, smaller ceremonial flames, or partially fireless formats may proliferate. Such changes would not necessarily mark the end of the Czech Walpurgis “Witches’ Night” tradition. On the contrary, they would confirm that the celebrations remain popular because they change. Its future will depend on whether local communities can continue to align cultural desires, economic practicality, and environmental responsibility.

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